

E3.2 Intermediate prototype of the inclusion of AIOps in the system

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List of Acronyms

3D	Three Dimension
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AIOps	AI Operations
AR	Augmented Reality
CD	Continuous Delivery
CI	Continuous Integration
6DoF	Six Degrees of Freedom
FPS	Frame per Second
HD	High Definition
HTC	Holographic-Type Communications
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
MEC	Multi-access Edge Computing
ML	Machine Learning
MLOps	Machine Learning Operations
NFV	Network Function Virtualization
NR	New Radio
QoE	Quality of Experience
RAN	Radio Access Network
SoA	State-of-the-Art
TD	Technological Domain
UE	User Equipment
UNICO	Universalización de Infraestructuras Digitales para la Cohesión
VNF	Virtual Network Function
VR	Virtual Reality
XR	Extended Reality

1 Introduction

Kubeflow is an open-source platform built on Kubernetes to simplify the deployment and management of machine learning (ML) workflows. It provides a comprehensive suite of tools and components tailored for ML development and production. With Kubeflow, users can use familiar tools like Jupyter Notebooks for experimentation, TensorFlow Extended (TFX) for building scalable pipelines, and model serving capabilities for deploying trained models. Kubeflow also facilitates metadata management, experiment tracking, hyperparameter tuning, and pipeline orchestration, empowering teams to collaborate effectively and achieve reproducibility in ML projects. By abstracting away infrastructure complexities and providing a unified platform, Kubeflow accelerates the development and deployment of ML applications, making it accessible to a broader audience of data scientists and ML practitioners. One of the key components of Kubeflow is the Kubeflow Pipelines. Kubeflow Pipelines is a platform for building, deploying, and managing end-to-end machine learning (ML) workflows on Kubernetes. It provides tools and components to create and manage complex ML workflows, allowing users to define, schedule, and run entire pipelines for training, evaluation, and deployment of machine learning models.

The workflows are constructed using reusable components, which encapsulate individual ML tasks such as data preprocessing, model training, evaluation, and inference. These components can be connected to form pipelines, enabling modular and scalable ML workflows. Kubeflow Pipelines offers visualization tools to visualize and track the progress of pipeline runs, making it easier to monitor the execution of each step and identify potential issues or bottlenecks in the workflow. This visualization and monitoring capability enhances the overall visibility and management of ML workflows.

Overall, Kubeflow Pipelines simplifies the process of building and managing machine learning workflows, enabling data scientists and ML engineers to focus on developing and deploying models efficiently and at scale. Its comprehensive features and seamless integration with Kubernetes and the Kubeflow ecosystem make it a powerful tool for accelerating ML development and deployment workflows.

In this respect, 6GENABLERS-AI aims at bridging the gap in holoportation and its intelligent orchestration by i) Distributing the holoportation service functions over the Edge-cloud continuum and ii) Developing native AI pipelines to automate the AI-enabled orchestration lifecycle, enabling a fast adaptation to the dynamicity of the holoportation service. This deliverable analyses the holoportation intelligent orchestration use case and defines the requirements thereof.

2 Installation

As mentioned earlier, Kubeflow Pipelines is a part of the Kubeflow components, but it also functions as an independent component. The installation process assumes that a Kubernetes Cluster is already running and configured accordingly. For a detailed installation guide for Kubernetes, please refer to the official documentation on their website.

<https://kubernetes.io/>

In addition to the Kubernetes cluster, we also need to install the Kubeflow Pipelines components. There are different distributions depending on the Cloud provider in which the Pipelines are going to be installed in. The more popular Cloud providers, such as Amazon Web Services (AWS), Google Cloud or Microsoft Azure. However, in this initial version we are going to install the pipelines in a local deployment. As the installation is going to be done over a Kubernetes cluster, the most straightforward process is to apply the corresponding manifest files using the previously installed kubectl command.

```
export PIPELINE_VERSION=2.1.0
kubectl apply -k "github.com/kubeflow/pipelines/manifests/kustomize/cluster-scoped-resources?ref=$PIPELINE_VERSION"
kubectl wait --for condition=established --timeout=60s crd/applications.app.k8s.io
kubectl apply -k "github.com/kubeflow/pipelines/manifests/kustomize/env/platform-agnostic-pns?ref=$PIPELINE_VERSION"
```

After successfully applying these manifests, the pods will take a couple of minutes to be established. After verifying that all the pods are running successfully using:

```
kubectl get po -A
```

We will forward the Kubeflow Pipelines dashboard to a local browser to take full advantage of the User Interface (UI) of the component.

```
kubectl port-forward -n kubeflow svc/ml-pipeline-ui 8080:80
```

The UI can be accessed using a browser at the following address:

```
http://localhost:8080/
```

For more information regarding the installation of Kubeflow Pipelines, please refer to the official website:

<https://www.kubeflow.org/docs/components/pipelines/>

3 Configuration

In a Kubeflow Pipeline, each component functions as a critical piece of the overall workflow, seamlessly connected through a conductive thread that orchestrates their interactions. Data Ingestion component retrieves or generates the necessary data for the pipeline. This could involve tasks such as fetching datasets from external sources, querying databases, or accessing files from storage systems. Once the data is obtained, it goes into the Data Preprocessing component.

Here, the data undergoes various transformations to prepare it for model training. This includes cleaning, normalization, feature engineering, and any other preprocessing tasks necessary to optimize the data for training. Once the data is preprocessed, it continues into the Model Training component.

In the Model Training phase, the machine learning model is trained using the preprocessed data. This involves running algorithms, optimizing parameters, and iterating on the model to achieve the desired performance metrics. Once trained, the model transitions into the Model Evaluation component. Here, the trained model is rigorously evaluated to assess its performance and effectiveness. Various metrics such as accuracy, precision, recall, and F1-score could be calculated using a separate dataset to gauge the model's efficacy. After evaluation, the model is ready to go into the Model Deployment phase.

In Model Deployment, the trained and evaluated model is deployed to a production environment, where it can serve predictions or classifications in real-time. This involves packaging the model, creating inference endpoints, and deploying them to a serving infrastructure. Finally, all these components are orchestrated by a Pipeline Orchestration component. This component coordinates the execution of individual components, manages dependencies, handles retries and failures, and ensures the smooth execution of the pipeline from start to finish. Together, these components and their conductive thread enable the automation, scalability, and reproducibility of machine learning pipelines in Kubeflow.

In conclusion, a pipeline component encapsulates a self-contained set of code designed to execute a singular step within the ML workflow. Components adhere to a component specification, which delineates the component's interface, the implementation details and the output artifacts. Technically speaking, each component is a containerized, independent entity that generates isolation of the code and therefore of the developing process in itself.

Technically speaking, this isolation is possible by using the Software Developing Kit (SDK) provided by Kubeflow, installed as follows:

```
pip install kfp
```

This library will allow us to use a decorator in our Python code to tell the code which parts are going to be used as a component in our Pipelines. The decorator for each Python definition is the following:

```
@dsl.component
def task1():
```

After having defined all of the Pipeline components, we need to gather them into the final Pipeline, using their respective outputs to form the logical workflow as needed. The decorator needed to generate the Pipeline is as follows:

```
@dsl.pipeline(name='')  
    task1 = task1()  
    task2 = task2(task1.output)  
    return
```

4 Usage

There are mainly two ways to get the pipelines working. The first one is using the recently created UI and import a YAML file with the configuration of the Pipelines. The YAML file is generated via:

```
compiler.Compiler().compile('pipeline', package_path='pipeline.yaml')
```

This will generate a YAML file with all the configuration required for our Pipeline that can be uploaded in the UI, using the respective button:

Figure 1 Kubeflow Pipelines User Interface.

After the YAML file has been submitted, the architecture of the Pipeline can be checked and tested with. It is worth noting that by using this UI option, the input parameters of the workflow should be inserted through the graphic interface. The second option to upload the file is to do it by using the following command:

```
client.create_run_from_pipeline_func(pipeline,
arguments=hyperparameters, experiment_name="test", namespace="kubeflow", enable_caching=True)
```

Using this approach allows to pass the hyperparameters through an in-environment variable, also automatically creating the experiment in the UI. It is also necessary to create a client so the Python KFP can talk with the already running Pipeline server.

```
client = kfp.Client(
    existing_token=TOKEN,
    host='http://localhost:8080/',
)
```

By using any of the two options, the Pipeline should be now accessible through the UI, and ready to run it.

Figure 2 Pipeline created in Kubeflow Pipelines dashboard.

For the complete code of the Pipelines, please refer to the respective GitLab repository:

https://gitlab.i2cat.net/rdprojects/6genablers/6genablers-ai/kubeflow-pipelines/-/blob/main/pipeline_6g.py

5 Conclusion

In conclusion, Kubeflow Pipelines emerges as a robust and versatile MLOps architecture, offering a comprehensive solution for managing the end-to-end lifecycle of machine learning workflows. Its ability to seamlessly integrate with Kubernetes clusters provides scalability and portability, enabling organizations to deploy ML models consistently across diverse computing environments. Kubeflow Pipelines' intuitive interface and declarative pipeline definitions simplify the orchestration of complex ML workflows, while its support for versioning and reproducibility ensures transparency and traceability throughout the model development process. Furthermore, Kubeflow Pipelines fosters collaboration among data scientists, engineers, and domain experts by facilitating the sharing of code, data, and model artifacts within a unified platform. By harnessing the virtues of Kubeflow Pipelines, researchers can accelerate the development, deployment, and management of ML models, ultimately driving innovation and unlocking new opportunities in the era of AI and machine learning.